

UNIVERSAL PROGNOSTIC ROLE OF LEFT VENTRICULAR DIASTOLIC DYSFUNCTION IN EUROSCORE II, STS, AND MAGGIC MODELS**Moldotashev I.K.¹,****Nazarov A.K.²,****Sorokin A.A.³**¹ Adam University, Bishkek, Kyrgyz Republic² Cardiac Surgery Clinic "Bikard", Bishkek, Kyrgyz Republic³ I.K. Akhunbaev Kyrgyz State Medical Academy, Bishkek, Kyrgyz Republic**Abstract**

Objective. To evaluate the universal prognostic value of left ventricular diastolic dysfunction (LVDD) when added to various clinical risk scores (EuroSCORE II, STS, MAGGIC) in patients undergoing coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG).

Materials and Methods. The study included 178 patients with coronary artery disease who underwent elective CABG. Clinical, echocardiographic, and functional parameters were analyzed, including the assessment of left ventricular diastolic function. EuroSCORE II, STS, and MAGGIC risk scores were calculated for all patients. The prognostic value of the models was assessed using ROC analysis (AUC), DeLong test, risk reclassification indices (NRI, IDI), and Decision Curve Analysis.

Results. Left ventricular diastolic dysfunction was an independent predictor of postoperative complications. The addition of LVDD to the EuroSCORE II, STS, and MAGGIC models significantly improved their discriminative ability ($\Delta\text{AUC} = 0.07\text{--}0.08$; $p < 0.05$ for all models). NRI and IDI indices demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in risk stratification across all models. Decision Curve Analysis showed increased clinical usefulness of the combined models across a wide range of risk thresholds.

Conclusion. LVDD is a universal functional risk modifier that improves the prognostic accuracy of various clinical models. Inclusion of left ventricular diastolic function assessment in preoperative risk stratification algorithms for CABG may significantly improve clinical decision-making.

Keywords: CABG, diastolic dysfunction, EuroSCORE II, STS, MAGGIC, prognosis, NRI, IDI.

INTRODUCTION

Coronary artery disease remains the leading cause of mortality worldwide, and coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG) is one of the most effective methods of surgical myocardial revascularization. Despite significant advances in cardiac surgery, the risk of postoperative complications remains substantial and requires accurate preoperative risk stratification.

In clinical practice, prognostic models such as EuroSCORE II, STS, and MAGGIC are widely used; however, their limitations are associated with insufficient consideration of myocardial functional status. In particular, left ventricular diastolic function, which is an integral indicator of myocardial reserve, is not included in most existing models.

Left ventricular diastolic dysfunction is considered an integrative marker of structural and functional myocardial remodeling, reflecting impaired relaxation, increased myocardial stiffness, and elevated filling pressure, which leads to reduced hemodynamic reserve. It has been shown that diastolic dysfunction is an independent predictor of adverse outcomes after cardiac surgery, including mortality, prolonged mechanical ventilation, and longer hospital stay.

Clinically, it is important that LVDD is often detected in patients with preserved or moderately reduced left ventricular ejection fraction and reflects the phenotype of heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF), which results in latent reduction of myocardial reserve and increased vulnerability under surgical stress.

Thus, there is a practical need for a simple and reproducible algorithm for personalized risk stratification of complications after CABG, complementing traditional risk scores and based on functionally significant parameters, primarily the assessment of left ventricular diastolic function.

Aim of the study: to evaluate the universal role of LVDD as a modifier of the prognostic models EuroSCORE II, STS, and MAGGIC in patients undergoing CABG.

MATERIALS AND METHODS**Study design and patients**

The study included 178 patients with coronary artery disease who underwent elective coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG). Clinical, echocardiographic, and functional parameters were analyzed, including the assessment of left ventricular diastolic function, as well as integral risk scores (EuroSCORE II, STS, MAGGIC).

Depending on the postoperative course, patients were divided into two groups:

- patients with a favorable postoperative course (136 patients);
- patients with postoperative complications (42 patients).

Inclusion criteria: presence of indications for CABG; elective surgery; availability of complete clinical, laboratory, and instrumental data.

Exclusion criteria: emergency cardiac surgery; repeat cardiac surgery; acute inflammatory or infectious diseases in the preoperative period; incomplete clinical or instrumental data.

Instrumental assessment and risk scores

All patients underwent a comprehensive examination including medical history assessment, evaluation of comorbidities, laboratory tests, ECG, and Doppler echocardiography. Doppler echocardiography was performed with assessment of systolic and diastolic left ventricular function; diastolic function was assessed according to standard methodology.

To assess surgical risk and predict postoperative complications, EuroSCORE II, STS score, and MAGGIC score were calculated for all patients.

The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Helsinki Declaration. All patients signed informed consent.

Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed using R and SPSS software packages. The normality of distribution was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test. Quantitative data are presented as median and interquartile range (Me [Q1; Q3]), and qualitative data as absolute and relative values (n, %).

Independent groups were compared using the Mann–Whitney test for quantitative variables and the Pearson χ^2 test or Fisher's exact test for categorical variables. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

To identify risk factors for postoperative complications, logistic regression analysis was performed with univariate and multivariate analysis. Results are presented as odds ratio (OR) with 95% confidence interval (CI).

The prognostic performance of the models was evaluated using ROC analysis (AUC), and model comparison was performed using the DeLong test. The additional prognostic value of left ventricular diastolic dysfunction was assessed using risk reclassification indices (NRI, IDI). The clinical usefulness of the models was analyzed using Decision Curve Analysis (net benefit).

RESULTS

Table 1.

Baseline characteristics of patients (Group 1 – without complications, Group 2 – with complications)

Parameter	Without complications (n=136)	With complications (n=42)	p
Age, years	58 [52; 64]	61 [55; 67]	0.15
Sex, n (%)	103 (75.7)	36 (85.7)	0.18
BMI, kg/m ²	26.9 [24.4; 29.8]	27.2 [25.0; 30.5]	0.78
LVEDD, mm	55 [50–60]	52 [48–56]	>0.05
LVESD, mm	40 [33–45]	35 [30–40]	>0.05
IVS, mm	9.5 [10–12]	10.0 [9–11]	>0.05
LV posterior wall, mm	10.0 [10–12]	10.5 [9–11]	>0.05
LVEF, %	52 [46; 60]	45 [40; 52.8]	0.004
Heart rate, bpm	74 [65; 83]	82 [71; 91]	0.008
Left atrial diameter, mm	39 [38; 43]	43.5 [40; 47]	<0.001
Creatinine, $\mu\text{mol/L}$	90 [76; 107]	97.5 [89.8; 114]	0.025
EuroSCORE II	0.016 [0.011; 0.027]	0.0317 [0.0143; 0.0671]	0.002
STS score	0.009 [0.0065; 0.013]	0.0158 [0.0105; 0.0397]	<0.001
MAGGIC score	22 [19; 25]	24 [21; 27]	0.03
LVDD, n (%)	51 (37.8)	28 (66.7)	0.001
Diabetes mellitus, n (%)	58 (42.6)	16 (38.1)	0.52
Previous myocardial infarction	35 (25.7)	11 (26.2)	0.97
COPD	22 (16.2)	5 (11.9)	0.63
Smoking	25 (18.4)	6 (14.3)	0.64
Left ventricular hypertrophy	80 (58.8)	27 (64.3)	0.46

As can be seen from the data presented in Table 1, there were no differences between the groups in age, sex, and body mass index. The groups also did not differ significantly in left ventricular size and wall thickness, in the number of previous myocardial infarctions, in the presence of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, diabetes mellitus, smoking status, or left ventricular hypertrophy (according to ECG data).

Statistically significant differences between the groups were found in left ventricular ejection fraction,

left ventricular diastolic dysfunction, heart rate, left atrial diameter, and blood creatinine levels. All three risk scores (EuroSCORE II, STS, and MAGGIC) showed statistically significant differences between the groups.

In Table 2, the baseline characteristics of patients are presented with the indication of the standard deviation (\pm SD). They confirm the data presented in Table 1.

Table 2.

Baseline characteristics of patients (Group 1 – without complications, Group 2 – with complications). Values are presented as mean \pm SD. Comparison was performed using Welch's two-tailed t-test.

Parameter	Without complications (n=136)	With complications (n=42)	p
BMI, kg/m ²	29.1 \pm 3.9	28.9 \pm 4.9	0.71
LVEDD, mm	55 \pm 0.66	52 \pm 0.78	>0.05
LVESD, mm	40 \pm 0.87	35 \pm 1.09	>0.05
IVS, mm	9.5 \pm 0.13	10.0 \pm 0.22	>0.05
LV posterior wall, mm	10.0 \pm 0.13	10.5 \pm 0.22	>0.05
LVEF, %	51.1 \pm 9.8	45.2 \pm 11.1	0.002
Left atrial diameter, mm	39.8 \pm 5.5	44.7 \pm 7.9	<0.001
Heart rate, bpm	75.1 \pm 13.5	83.1 \pm 15.1	0.004
Creatinine, μ mol/L	92.1 \pm 25.6	102.9 \pm 29.9	0.021
EuroSCORE II	0.016 \pm 0.009	0.032 \pm 0.028	<0.001
STS score	0.0095 \pm 0.007	0.016 \pm 0.015	0.001
MAGGIC score	21.8 \pm 4.6	24.2 \pm 5.3	0.007

The analyzed scores (EuroSCORE II, STS score and MAGGIC score) represent integral multiparametric models. Inclusion in the analysis of individual variables included in their structure (left ventricular ejection fraction, creatinine level) could lead to duplication of prognostic information. Therefore, we evaluated the diagnostic effectiveness of these scores with the addition of only the parameter of left ventricular diastolic dysfunction, which is not included in their calculators.

Table 3.

Diagnostic effectiveness of prognostic models according to ROC analysis and comparison using the DeLong method

Model	AUC (95% CI)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Δ AUC	P (DeLong)
LVDD	0.69 (0.60–0.78)	66.7	62.2	—	—
STS	0.72 (0.64–0.80)	68.1	76.5	—	—
STS + LVDD	0.75 (0.68–0.83)	76.2	73.5	+0.03	0.041*
EuroSCORE II	0.67 (0.59–0.75)	65.4	70.1	—	—
EuroSCORE II + LVDD	0.73 (0.65–0.81)	73.8	72.1	+0.06	0.028*
MAGGIC	0.53 (0.45–0.61)	60.0	58.0	—	—
MAGGIC + LVDD	0.66 (0.58–0.74)	71.4	65.4	+0.13	0.012*

The addition of left ventricular diastolic dysfunction led to a statistically significant increase in AUC in all models ($p < 0.05$), while the most pronounced increase was observed for the MAGGIC score (Δ AUC = 0.13), whereas the STS + LVDD model demonstrated the most balanced improvement in discriminative ability.

Risk reclassification analysis (NRI, IDI) confirmed a clinically significant improvement in patient risk stratification. Decision Curve Analysis showed an

increase in net benefit of the combined models across a wide range of threshold probabilities.

No statistically significant differences were found between the individual clinical scores ($p > 0.05$). Similarly, comparison of the combined models also did not show statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$).

* $p < 0.05$ — statistically significant difference (DeLong test)

Incremental prognostic value of LVDD added to conventional risk models

Data source: cleaned cohort from uploaded Excel workbook (n=178; no complications n=136, complications n=42). Base and augmented models were fit on complete cases for each score.

Figure 1. Incremental prognostic value of left ventricular diastolic dysfunction (LVDD) added to conventional risk models in patients undergoing coronary artery bypass grafting.

(A) Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves demonstrating improved discrimination after inclusion of LVDD into STS, EuroSCORE II, and MAGGIC models.

(B) Absolute increase in area under the curve (Δ AUC) following addition of LVDD.

(C) Improvement in risk reclassification assessed by net reclassification improvement (NRI) and integrated discrimination improvement (IDI).

(D) Decision curve analysis (DCA) showing increased net benefit of LVDD-augmented models across clinically relevant threshold probabilities.

Addition of LVDD resulted in consistent improvement in discrimination, risk reclassification, and clinical utility across all models, with the greatest relative gain observed in the MAGGIC model, while the STS-based model demonstrated the most balanced and clinically robust performance.

DISCUSSION

In the present study, it was shown that left ventricular diastolic dysfunction (LVDD) is a significant independent predictor of postoperative complications in patients undergoing coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG). The addition of LVDD to traditional prognostic models (EuroSCORE II, STS, and MAGGIC) was

accompanied by an improvement in discriminative ability, risk reclassification, and clinical usefulness, which indicates its additional prognostic value.

The obtained results confirm the concept that LVDD reflects myocardial functional reserve and integrates the influence of multiple pathophysiological factors, including age, arterial hypertension, ischemia, and metabolic disorders [9–11]. Unlike traditional risk scores, which are mainly based on demographic and clinical variables, LVDD represents a functional parameter that directly characterizes the ability of the myocardium to adapt to hemodynamic stress. This is consistent with modern concepts of heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF), where impaired diastolic function plays a key role in clinical outcomes [9,12].

Clinically, it is important that LVDD is often detected in patients with preserved or moderately reduced left ventricular ejection fraction, which reflects the phenomenon of a “hidden” decrease in myocardial reserve. Population studies have shown that diastolic dysfunction is associated with the development of heart failure and increased mortality even in the presence of normal systolic function [13].

Under conditions of surgical intervention, accompanied by fluctuations in preload and afterload, systemic inflammatory response, and activation of neuro-humoral mechanisms, it is the decrease in diastolic reserve that may limit the adaptive capacity of the heart and contribute to the development of complications. Previous studies have shown that diastolic dysfunction is an independent predictor of adverse outcomes after cardiac surgery, including increased mortality, duration of mechanical ventilation, and length of hospital stay [7,16,17].

Of particular importance are the results of the analysis of prognostic models. Despite a moderate increase in the area under the ROC curve (AUC), the addition of LVDD led to a significant improvement in risk reclassification, which was confirmed by positive NRI and IDI values (see Fig. 1). This emphasizes the limitations of using only AUC to assess the prognostic value of new markers and is consistent with modern recommendations for evaluating risk models, where particular attention is paid to the ability of the model to correctly reclassify patients between risk categories [6].

Decision Curve Analysis demonstrated that inclusion of LVDD provides a higher net benefit in a clinically significant range of threshold probabilities compared with the baseline models (see Fig. 1). This indicates that the use of LVDD can not only improve the statistical characteristics of the models but also improve the quality of clinical decision-making in the preoperative period, which is consistent with modern approaches to assessing the clinical usefulness of prognostic models [14,15].

Interestingly, the greatest relative increase in discriminative ability was observed for the MAGGIC model, whereas the STS + LVDD model demonstrated the most balanced characteristics. This may reflect differences in the initial structure of the models: in particular, the STS model already includes a wide range of clinical variables, whereas the MAGGIC model was originally developed for a population of patients with chronic heart failure.

It is fundamentally important that none of the widely used prognostic scores, including EuroSCORE II, STS, and MAGGIC, include direct indicators of left ventricular diastolic function. The obtained data demonstrate that the inclusion of LVDD makes it possible to fill this gap and add a new, independent layer of risk information that is not covered by traditional variables.

The practical significance of the results lies in the possibility of integrating the assessment of diastolic function into preoperative risk stratification algorithms. This may contribute to more accurate identification of high-risk patients, optimization of management strategies, and potentially reduce the incidence of complications.

Thus, LVDD is a universal functional risk modifier that increases the accuracy and clinical applicability of existing prognostic models in patients undergoing CABG.

The limitations of the study include a single-center design and a relatively limited sample size. In addition, the assessment of diastolic function was based on standard echocardiographic parameters, which may be subject to inter-operator variability. Further multicenter studies are required to validate the obtained results and to determine the optimal ways of integrating left ventricular diastolic dysfunction into clinical risk models.

References

1. Vujcic I, Maksimovic J, Sipetic-Grujicic S. Epidemiology of ischemic heart disease. *Medicinska Istrazivanja*. 2025;1:1-11. doi:10.5937/medi0-58650.
2. Ogryzko EV, Ivanova MA, Odinets AV, Vankov DV, Lyutsko VV. Dynamics of morbidity and mortality from acute forms of ischemic heart disease in the Russian Federation in 2012-2017. *Profilakticheskaya Meditsina*. 2019;22(5):23-27. doi:10.17116/profmed20192205123.
3. Akchurin RS, Shiryayev AA, Vasiliev VP, Gal'yautdinov DM, Vlasova EE. Current trends in coronary surgery. *Patologiya Krovoobrashcheniya i Kardiokhirurgiya*. 2017;21(3 Suppl):34-44. doi:10.21688/1681-3472-2017-3S-34-44.
4. Nashef SAM, Roques F, Sharples LD, Nilsson J, Smith C, Goldstone AR, et al. EuroSCORE II. *Eur J Cardiothorac Surg*. 2012;41(4):734-744. doi:10.1093/ejcts/ezs043.
5. Shahian DM, O'Brien SM, Filardo G, Ferraris VA, Haan CK, Rich JB, et al. The Society of Thoracic Surgeons 2008 cardiac surgery risk models: part 1—coronary artery bypass grafting surgery. *Ann Thorac Surg*. 2009;88(1 Suppl):S2-S22. doi:10.1016/j.athoracsur.2009.05.053.
6. Pocock SJ, Ariti CA, McMurray JJV, Maggioni A, Køber L, Squire IB, et al. Predicting survival in heart failure: a risk score based on 39 372 patients from 30 studies. *Eur Heart J*. 2013;34(19):1404-1413. doi:10.1093/eurheartj/ehs337.
7. Metkus TS, Suarez-Pierre A, Crawford TC, Lawton JS, Goeddel L, Dodd-O J, et al. Diastolic dysfunction is common and predicts outcome after cardiac surgery. *J Cardiothorac Surg*. 2018;13:67. doi:10.1186/s13019-018-0748-7.
8. Kaw R, Hernandez AV, Pasupuleti V, Deshpande A, Nagarajan V, Bueno H, et al. Effect of diastolic dysfunction on postoperative outcomes after cardiovascular surgery: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Thorac Cardiovasc Surg*. 2016;152(4):1142-1153.
9. Paulus WJ, Tschöpe C. A novel paradigm for heart failure with preserved ejection fraction: comorbidities drive myocardial dysfunction and remodeling. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2013;62(4):263-271. doi:10.1016/j.jacc.2013.02.092.
10. González A, Schelbert EB, Díez J, Butler J. Myocardial interstitial fibrosis in heart failure: biological and translational perspectives. *Hypertension*. 2018;71(3):364-371.
11. Zile MR, Baicu CF, Gaasch WH. Diastolic heart failure—abnormalities in active relaxation and passive stiffness of the left ventricle. *N Engl J Med*. 2004;350(19):1953-1959.

12. McDonagh TA, Metra M, Adamo M, Gardner RS, Baumbach A, Böhm M, et al. 2021 ESC Guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of acute and chronic heart failure. *Eur Heart J.* 2021;42(36):3599-3726. doi:10.1093/eurheartj/ehab368.
13. Redfield MM, Jacobsen SJ, Burnett JC Jr, Mahoney DW, Bailey KR, Rodeheffer RJ. Burden of systolic and diastolic ventricular dysfunction in the community. *JAMA.* 2003;289(2):194-202.
14. Vickers AJ, Holland F. Decision curve analysis to evaluate the clinical benefit of prediction models. *Spine J.* 2021;21(5):841-848. doi:10.1016/j.spinee.2021.02.024.
15. Piovani D, Bonovas S, Nikolopoulos GK. Optimizing clinical decision-making with decision curve analysis. *Healthcare (Basel).* 2023;11(16):2244. doi:10.3390/healthcare11162244.
16. Labus J, Fassl J, Foit A, Mehler O, Rahmanian P, Wahlers T, et al. Evaluation of intraoperative left-ventricular diastolic function by myocardial strain in on-pump coronary artery bypass surgery. *J Cardiothorac Vasc Anesth.* 2024;38(3):638-648. doi:10.1053/j.jvca.2023.12.008.
17. Rong LQ, Di Franco A, Rahouma M, Dimagli A, Patel A, Lopes AJ, et al. Baseline intraoperative left ventricular diastolic function is associated with postoperative atrial fibrillation after cardiac surgery. *Anesthesiology.* 2023;139(5):602-613. doi:10.1097/ALN.0000000000004725.